

HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM FOR PERSONS WITH DISABILITIES: THE EXPERIENCE OF JAPAN

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Abstract. *This article reveals the relevance of studying the problem of organizing inclusive education in the higher education system. Based on the example of Japanese universities, Tsukuba University and the University of Technology for the Visually Impaired, the experience in organizing education for people with disabilities is summarized. The materials of the article reflect the results of the author's scientific internship under the program "Inclusive education in high-tech education system of Japan", conducted within the framework of the Grant project of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan "Formation of professional self-determination of students with special educational needs as a national strategy in the field of inclusive education of the Republic of Kazakhstan".*

Keywords: *inclusive education, inclusion, persons with disabilities, students with special educational needs.*

Education of disabled people and persons with disabilities is one of the problems whose relevance has not lost-finds its significance both in science and in practice. The policy proclaimed in many countries to ensure the availability of quality education at all levels stipulated by law for all segments of the population presupposes a continuous search for innovative models that meet this requirement, new forms and ways of organizing training.

Currently, the problem of obtaining higher education for people with disabilities and people with disabilities has a priority position in the practice of foreign countries in Eastern and Western Europe, the USA, Japan, Russia, etc. Aismontas B.B., studying the problem of vocational training for people with disabilities, came to the conclusion that in the most developed countries of the world great attention is paid to solving the problem of ensuring access of people with disabilities to vocational education, which ensures complete independence and economic independence of citizens with limited opportunities news. Ensuring equal opportunities to receive education for people with disabilities is an important part implementation of the principles of independent living for people with disabilities [1].

However, researchers on improving inclusive education identify the following problems in this area:

1) there is no systemic support for the learning process of students with disabilities and disabilities in vocational education programs, including through the use of information resources and technologies adapted to user needs;

2) there is no methodology for the development and adaptation of training and information educational resources for higher professional education programs to the needs of users with disabilities of various nosologies;

3) there is no open information and educational environment and a unified educational Internet portal designed to solve the problems of: vocational education and social adaptation of students with disabilities and disabilities; providing access to optimal adaptive educational technologies; organizing psychological and pedagogical support for training, vocational rehabilitation and orientation; providing access to mechanisms for promoting employment and effective employment developed by universities.

4) traditional conditions for organizing education in valid persons and persons with disabilities in the system government institutions do not fully ensure the quality national competitive level of education.

5) the integration of experience accumulated by the association of universities is not developed; call for students with disabilities to enter the education system ties, etc. [2].

In this regard, the study and implementation of international experience in organizing inclusive education in foreign countries, in particular such as Japan, is very relevant and timely.

It should be noted that the success of Japan, the second economic power in the world, is largely associated with a high level of education. It is no coincidence that Japan is called a great educated power. This country has always attached great importance to education. The desire for a higher status is a characteristic of the Japanese mentality. Throughout the history of the country, education has been an enduring spiritual value, one of the priorities of state policy, and a basic component of the economic “Japanese miracle” [3].

Japan is one of the leading countries in the implementation of inclusive education at all stages of education, from primary school to higher and secondary specialized education. The works of Japanese scientists (Kaoru Yamaguchi., Ellington L., Futao, Huang, etc.) reflected the experience of the country's strategy for the development of inclusive and special education [4, 6,9,12].

The legislative basis for creating a system of inclusive education at all stages, special support and patronage programs in Japan is the “Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities” [7]. To coordinate efforts to promote inclusive education in Japan, the National Center for Support of Persons with Disabilities, the Japan Student Support Organization, etc. were created.

The Japanese education system helps to blur differences between social groups. A representative of any class who graduates, for example, from the University of Tokyo, already belongs to the clan of its graduates, which provides him with a high status in society. At all levels of education, greater freedom of choice, flexibility and variety of learning are provided with an emphasis on the development of creative abilities. Stimulation of lifelong education continues with a shift in focus to learning throughout a person’s life [5]. This allows you to remain an active member of society, taking into account the 80-year life cycle of the Japanese people. Japanese legislation has an article offering preferential conditions and tax incentives for companies that provide jobs to graduates with disabilities, but even despite the benefits, they try to select only qualified and well-trained personnel.

Dronishinets N.P., Filatova I.A., studying the state policy for the development of special education in Japan, note that it is here that the social and humanistic orientation of state policy is especially clearly manifested, when the government makes every effort to ensure that children with developmental problems (blind, deaf, mentally retarded, etc.), train and educate, adapt them to life [3].

One of the key factors for the successful implementation of inclusive education in Japan is staffing. Kazakh scientists (Shkutina L.A., Abildina S.K., Yanek D., Rymkhanova A.R.), studying the features of the Japanese system of teacher training, note that teachers undergo special training to work with children with special educational needs, so how working with children with SEN requires additional knowledge and skills in special teaching methods, psychology and medicine [11].

Japan has made great strides in higher education for people with disabilities. In the article by S.S. Kolyshkina, devoted to the analysis of higher education of people with disabilities in Japan, identifies two directions in the process of including people with disabilities in the life of Japanese society, including access to education: the elimination of “environmental” and the elimination of “attitude” barriers. “Environmental” barriers are eliminated both in the process of reconstructing the existing infrastructure of universities, taking into account the new architectural requirements of a barrier-free environment, and by developing individual trajectories for the movement of students with limited mobility across the territory of the university. “Attitude” barriers are overcome with the help of intra-university volunteer assistance programs for students with disabilities, which involves students who have completed special preparatory courses, as well as municipal and state programs for the socialization of people with disabilities [8].

There are currently three and a half million disabled people in Japan. Of these, 370 thousand are working disabled people. Among this number of workers are 60 thousand deaf people. 34 percent of all universities and colleges accept students with hearing impairments. “The main trend that is successfully developing in the education system on a national scale,” notes O.A. Oreshkina, is the creation of autonomous coordination centers for students with disabilities in each of the host universities. Currently, this project operates in 45 universities and colleges in Japan” [10].

The author of this article, within the framework of the Grant project of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan “Formation of professional self-determination of students with special educational needs as a national strategy in the field of inclusive education of the Republic of Kazakhstan”, completed a scientific internship under the program “Inclusive education in high school education system of Japan”, which made it possible to get acquainted with the experience of a number of universities in organizing inclusive higher education.

As part of this program, we held an official visit to Tsukuba University of Technology for students with disabilities. Let us dwell on the experience of this Japanese university.

In 2004, the National University Corporation Tsukuba University of Technology (NTUT) launched the PEPNet Japan Project to create a network of vocational education programs in Japan. In 2003, before the start of this project, the structure of a national university corporation was created - Tsukuba University of Technology. It is the only university in Japan specifically authorized by the Japanese Ministry of Education to implement special programs for the hearing and visually impaired. Initially, training was carried out in four-year applied bachelor's programs, but later master's programs were opened. NTUT currently has nine master's degrees in engineering and technology programs. It is important that before NTUT launched as a university corporation, a special structure was created there to provide network support for its activities throughout Japan. Only after this was PEPNet Japan established. The mission of PEPNet Japan is to provide support to people with hearing and vision disabilities in educational institutions in Japan, to ensure the

exchange of experience and training - since Japan has adopted this model within the framework of the PEN International project. PEPNet Japan develops effective technologies to support students with hearing and vision disabilities, and provides assistance to all colleges and universities nationwide that educate them.

NTUT is the main coordinator and fund manager for all universities in the network, each of which in turn provides support to disabled people in regional universities and colleges. Tsukuba-Technology Access Center - Tsukuba Center for the development and implementation of technologies, is a social project to support people with hearing impairments throughout Japan. The network develops relevant, in-demand materials, exchanges experience, disseminates information, develops and implements training and retraining programs for teachers and staff, educational materials and technologies, such as remote sign language interpretation, communication services for the deaf and hard of hearing based on speech recognition programs.

The university has established a medical faculty (with core disciplines such as acupuncture, ignipuncture and physiotherapy), which admits up to 120 people. Some students are also admitted to the Faculty of Information Systems Design. The University has established a Center for Supporting Research in the Field of Education for People with Disabilities, the goal of which is to improve teaching methods in higher education for people with disabilities and help future applicants.

In order to support people with low vision in obtaining higher education, the State Examination Center for Admission to Universities carries out a lot of work to provide support - from preparing examination sheets in Braille to assessing the work of applicants, also done in raised dotted font. For these individuals, the exam time increases by 1.5 times, and applicants can take it in a separate room using a Braille typewriter, using a magnifying glass and other auxiliary devices.

NTUT annually conducts seminars on the technological training of coordinators - authorized representatives from each of the universities included in the network, who, in turn, then implement these technologies in their universities, and then disseminate the acquired knowledge to sponsored organizations.

Let us dwell on the experience of one of the largest universities, the University of Tsukuba (Japan), a national university that was chosen by the Japanese government among the nine best national universities of the highest type as part of the Top Global University Project. The University of Tsukuba, one of the oldest universities in Japan, included in the top 10 Japanese, top 250 world universities, is among the Japanese universities with the largest number of Nobel laureates, three graduates of the university received the Nobel Prize in physics in 1965 and 1973, and in chemistry – in 2000.

The following faculties and institutes are open within the structure of the University: School of Art and Design; School of Sports Education; Faculty of Humanities and Culture; School of Psychology and Pedagogy; Faculty of Information Technologies; Faculty of Ecology; Faculty of Medicine; School of Science and Engineering; Faculty of International Relations.

The university provides training in international undergraduate programs taught in English in the field of life and environmental sciences (specialties: biology, agrobiological, geoscience), international social sciences, interdisciplinary engineering, global problems and medicine.

The University of Tsukuba is the first university in Japan to accept students with special educational needs. Students with special needs are increasing every year; there are 49 thousand of

them at the university, which is 1.5% of the total number. In 2001, an Official Body was created at the university, whose activities were aimed at integrating students into society. The Medical Center established at the university provides support for the health of students.

In January 2014, the Human Resource Development Bureau and the “Center for the Development and Support of Students with Various Needs” began operating at the university.

The support system for students with special needs at the University of Tsukuba includes:

1. Providing assistance to students with special education needs in obtaining a quality education.

2. Creation of special conditions in classrooms taking into account gender equality.

3. Assignment of assistant tutors. A tutor is a student who helps students with special educational needs and accompanies them in the educational process. They undergo special training to master the skills to provide assistance and support to students with developmental disabilities.

4. Work with teachers. Organization of advanced training courses for university teachers.

The Project is being implemented at the University of Tsukuba “*Support for people with different needs on the psycho-emotional spectrum.*”

The project is being implemented in the following areas:

1. Conducting scientific research at the expense of the state and non-state sectors and testing in university practice. Dissemination of experience outside the university.

2. Development of special methods and techniques for assessing the diverse needs of students.

3. Scientific research into the diversity of brain development in students with special needs. Perceptions of students with diverse brain development.

The university website contains “*A manual to help students organize their educational process*”, developed by student tutors. This manual includes the following sections.

Student assessment:

1). Questioning all students to study their psychological and other needs. Identifying students with a specific focus.

2). Individual assessment taking into account a diverse range of functions (interview, questionnaires). On this basis, individual support plans are developed. Communication is very important. Mutual assistance, stimulation based on needs.

3). Organization of tutoring activities to provide assistance in writing essays, design works, dissertations.

Examples of working with students with different needs:

- for the visually impaired (magnifying font):

- for the hearing impaired (hearing aids)

- for students on the psycho-emotional spectrum.

The University pays great attention to establishing partnerships with other organizations to provide social services to students with special health needs and support them outside of the classroom. Particular attention is paid to career guidance work and student employment. According to Japanese legislation in 2016, enterprises are required to accept students with disabilities.

One of the important missions of the university is to disseminate information outside the university so that other educational institutions can benefit from their experience. The websites of various companies, foundations, and educational institutions are used.

Analysis of international experience in organizing higher inclusive education in Japan allows us to draw the following conclusions.

- features of the national educational system, expressed in legislative acts in relation to people with disabilities, influence approaches to the implementation of inclusive education in universities;

- Japan's experience in introducing a network model of academic support for people with disabilities is of significant interest. Each university has a special structure that provides coordination, organizational and consulting services to all disabled people studying at the university.

- attracts attention to the creation on the basis of leading special centers: "centers of accessible technologies", "centers of resource provision", the activities of which are coordinated by the Unified National Center for Technical Support. An indicator of the effectiveness of the network is the presence of transformations on a national scale and an increase in the number of people involved in inclusive education.

- international experience indicates the need to create a special structure in universities - a coordination, organizational, consulting resource structure designed to solve the problems of people with disabilities in these universities. It is economically feasible to diversify the functions of such structures in different universities, depending on what needs of students with disabilities this university solves.

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